

Investigating the Role of Film Lighting and Its Effect on the Audience's Emotional Response

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Abstract: Light is a vital element in the world without which nothing can be seen. Lighting is one of the vital aspects in the art and techniques of cinematography and filmmaking. The role of light in filmmaking is very important in creating atmosphere, environment, defining characters and creating visual effects. Filmmakers can convey their stories and emotions to the audience in the best way by using lighting. The current study examined the impact of three film lighting styles on participants' emotional responses. The light styles - High Key, Low Key, and Available Light – were selected based on Film theory. Thus, this study combines Media Effects and Film literature to empirically study the impact of structural elements of film on media audiences.

Significant relationship between different lighting styles and the emotional response of viewers was found. Participants who viewed the film in Low-Key lighting reported significantly more feelings of mystery, suspense, malice, intrigue, and other uneasy feelings associated with Low Key lighting. Surprisingly, Low Key lighting

also elicited higher levels of emotional response in more happy and positive emotions.

Though this is just the first empirical study of emotional responses in relation to film lighting style, significant results were found. Further studies must be conducted to develop a database and to provide more support to the findings in this study as the results indicate a relationship between film lighting and emotional response that has been indicated in film literature. This relationship can be empirically tested with significant results.

Keywords: Audience; Effects of lighting; Emotional reaction of the audience; Light, Lighting.

Introduction

“Lighting is to film what music is to opera” – C.B. Demille [Brown 1996]

“When people look at a beautiful countryside, we like to derive pleasure from it. We receive light sensations of different colors, different wavelengths reflected by the various objects all over the field of vision. This concert of light is similar to the one played by a hundred different instruments, in other words, a symphony of visual music” [Alton 1995]

For the last 100 years, the moving image has been illuminated with specific lighting styles defined and practiced by filmmakers. Ideally, if a filmmaker is performing his or her job correctly, the audience member should never be conscious of all the theory, methodology, and

craft the lighting designer is manipulating to create a deep and engaging viewing experience. Nevertheless, filmmakers work very hard to bring audiences experiences that will make them “feel they are right there in the movie,” or are experiencing presence (Lombard & Ditton, 1997). The goal is to make the viewer Genres such as comedy, drama, romance, science fiction, fantasy, and mystery, have been defined since the earliest forms of human storytelling. As cinema and film lighting theory developed, different lighting techniques grew to become associated with different types of stories to provoke audience emotional response and assist in narrative interpretation. These lighting styles used to enhance film’s power to impact audiences’ emotional response and narrative interpretation have been practiced for the last century but have not been examined by empirical study of how the audience actually responds to various lighting styles.

The importance of research

This research is clearly related to the effect of film lighting on the emotional reactions of the audience. By examining the three styles of lighting High Key, Low Key and Available and analyzing their results, this study helps to enrich the knowledge in the field of the effects of light on human emotions and emphasizes the link between media theories and film literature. The obtained results show that there is a significant relationship between light and negative and positive emotions of the audience. The obtained results show a significant relationship between light and negative and positive emotions of the audience, so that low-key lighting not only evokes emotions such as mystery and excitement, but also creates more positive emotions. Therefore, the importance of this research is not only in its findings but also in the opportunities it creates for future studies.

Research objectives

1. Analysis of the impact dimensions: Examining the aspects of the effect of light on the feelings and emotions of the audience.
2. Knowledge of genres: Familiarity with lighting genres and its application in film.
3. Revealing the importance of lighting: Examining the importance of lighting in determining the time and place of the story and creating visually impressive spaces.
4. Increasing public awareness: Increasing awareness about the importance of light and its conscious use in cinema.

Research questions

Main question:

What effect does lighting have on evoking the audience's emotional response?

Sub questions:

1. How do different elements of light (such as intensity, color and direction of light) create certain emotions in the viewer?
2. Can lighting reduce or increase feelings of empathy or happiness in viewers?
3. Is it possible to make the emotional effects on the audience deeper and more lasting by changing the light in a scene?

Necessity of research

Research on the effect of lighting styles in cinema on the emotional reactions of the audience is necessary, while the importance of light in creating emotional experiences is recognized by films, but few empirical studies have been done in this field. Investigating how different lighting styles affect the emotions of the audience can help filmmakers improve their lighting methods and use it as a tool to enhance the narrative and communicate emotionally with the audience. Also, identifying lighting patterns related to different genres can help content producers to have more impact, and this research can lead to a deeper understanding of the art of cinema and its effects on society.

Research Methodology

This research has been done in a review method. In this way, the available sources in the field of lighting, has been In order to investigate the effect of light, its role in determining the characters of the film and the plot has been discussed. First, scientific articles, books and authoritative sources related to the subject of the collection have been qualitatively examined, so that the importance and effect of lighting in conveying the message, the purpose based on the script and evoking emotions in the audience have been examined.

Findings

Though neither the field of Film nor the field of Communication have conducted empirical studies to measure the emotional impact of film lighting, there is rich history and theory speculating emotional response from different lighting conditions. There are also connections in the fields of Psychology and Architecture where similar theories are discussed and some empirical testing has been completed. The field of Communication also has developed a general theoretical category into which testing the effect on film lighting on emotional response fits. The following is a literature review of how all these different fields support the theory and testing of audiences' emotional response to film lighting

Light as Ennery

No mater what generates it, emits it, or reflects it, light is energy: energy waves of Electromagnetic radiation that happen to live in a zone of frequencies known as the visible spectrum.

Light itself is invisible, but the surface materials of objects can reflect light in such a way that the human visual system sees it as white, black, or combinations of colors or hues from violet, through blue, green, yellow, and orange, to red.

When white light (all color wavelengths combined equally) hits an object, and that object's surface reflects all wavelengths equally, you see that object as white.

If an object absorbs all light energy wavelengths, then the object is seen as black. It reflects no significant light energy for you to detect.

When an object absorbs all colors but reflects only one wavelength, you see that object as being that one reflected color. So à yellow object appears yellow because its surface is absorbing all light wavelengths except those from the yellow area of the spectrum.

–Not all light sources emit pure white light in a balanced spectrum, but luckily we have ways of measuring the color of light.

As with many forms of energy, light can dissipate across distances. A lighting fixture close to your scene or subject can deliver its light energy more efficiently and at an appropriate level for

its intensity (often measured in lumens, lux, or footcandles). As you move that same fixture further from your scene or subject, the effective output remains the same, but the light energy that reaches your subject across this greater distance will be diminished. Be aware of this “drop-off” when you place your lights and/ or your subject in your shooting environment. The more powerful the lighting fixture and the more focusable the beam intensity, the greater chance you have of projecting that light source across a larger distance. If you wish to learn more about the mathematical formula surrounding the measurement and calculation of light drop-off, then check out the inverse square law (J.Bowen, 2018, p. 123).

Lighting History

A three dimensional world is how humans perceive reality, but people do not actually “see” the world around them. Humans see light reflecting off of objects in the everyday world. Our reality is constructed completely of light waves bringing us visual information, which we compute into thoughts, interpretations, and emotions. The human eye is identical to the first models of the camera, or camera obscura. It uses the effect of light passing through a small hole, or iris, and projecting an image upside down on the other side of the hole. A reflective surface flips the image back around and light can now be observed as a reality. Where the light passing through the human eye is immediately interpreted as 3- dimensional by the human brain, the image projected from a camera is only 2-dimensional. It has taken cinematographers and filmmakers many years to develop the technology and skill to sculpt and manipulate light for the reconstruction a three dimensional moving image.

These advances in lighting technology enhanced the theater experience, but when motion picture creation began in 1888, cameras could only get a decent exposure when using exterior daylight. Early film sets such as Thomas Edison’s Black Maria, had retractable roofs open to the sky. Interior lighting was not widely used until the introduction of White Flame Carbon Arcs in 1912. They were very loud and dangerous to use on sets, while tungsten lights, also invented at the same time, were safer and eventually became the predominant film light when panchromatic film stock was invented in 1927, which was sensitive to all light wavelengths (Brown, 1996).

A constant force in storytelling. “In visual storytelling, few elements are as effective and as powerful as light and color. They have the ability to reach the viewers at a purely emotional gut level” (Brown, 2012, p. 8). Perhaps because of the visceral nature of spiritual motivation and emotional reaction to light, the lighting styles theorized to be critical in the illumination and visual display of our developed genres remain solidly connected through time. Lighting Styles.

Cinematic Lighting

Since the emergence of photography and film, cinematic lighting has existed; however, despite changes in lighting technology, it continues to exist in a satisfying manner. "Most lighting techniques remain consistent for creating attractive and emotional images" (Shaffer and Salvato, 1984). "Lighting can change the surroundings and mood, and it can also affect the emotions of the viewer in a way that helps in better understanding the narrative" (Huang et al., 2014).

There is no difference between lighting in animation films and live-action films; the only difference is in the lighting methods used. Nowell (2017) suggested that lighting design in live-action films involves rapidly staging and framing each scene, requiring more creativity in composition because every process during filming affects each other. In contrast, lighting in 3D animation is usually pre-planned. Art directors in the production of 3D animated films also have a more complex style and design of lighting for the entire film. Lights are expressed as logical

sources. Additionally, when clear light is influenced by actual light sources, it becomes logical. On the other hand, logical lighting only considers the direction of lighting and produces visually appealing images (Nowell, 2017). Nowell (2017) also points out that "the style of lighting is not only for beautifying the shot, but it is also a fundamental part of cinematic lighting and storytelling.

A very important aspect before designing lighting is understanding the narrative behind the different scenes. When designing a scene according to the story, the use of color is truly significant. If the scene is overly lit, it likely conveys a specific emotion to the viewer. Conversely, dim and dark lighting generally represents threat. Sharp shadows usually indicate weakness, while soft light signifies a calm and gentle environment. Lighting can lead to reactions from the viewer by influencing the image, creating tension, sparking curiosity, and also determining the atmosphere. During the lighting design process, particularly in cinema, there are many objectives; however, two primary goals of a lighting designer are storytelling and creating an atmosphere to enhance the viewer's sense of belonging (Sugiarto, Widiastuti, 2020, pp. 161-162).

Film Lighting

Cinematic theory suggests that audience members experiencing a film lit in the noir style will interpret the highly shadowed, dark, and contrasting images with feelings of danger, suspense, depression, mystery, and evil. Characters in this mode should be interpreted as having evil intentions, being manipulative and untrustworthy. Cinematographers lighting a comedy use bright lighting set ups, less contrast, and a slick, shiny look to trigger emotional responses of joy, enlightenment, honesty, and happiness. In this lighting style, characters are interpreted as good hearted, funny, lovable, and heroic. For Mumble core, the raw realistic lighting is intended to give the audience the feeling of reality and truth. Audience members are thought to connect with these characters as though they could be from an audience member's life.

Cinematographers use these lighting approaches to enhance a movie's plot, characters, theme, style, and overall mood.

High Key

Although High-key lighting is a style of lighting for film, television, or photography that aims to reduce the lighting ratio present in the scene. This was originally done partly for technological reasons, since early film and television did not deal well with high contrast ratios, but now is used to suggest an upbeat mood. It is often used in works of comedy. High-key lighting is usually quite homogeneous and free from dark shadows. The terminology comes from the higher balance in the ratio between the key light and the fill light in a traditional three-point lighting setup) Tom, 2005, p. 81).

While High Key lighting, a style that brightly lights characters and set in a flat wash of illumination, was the first and only lighting style operable in early film, it found its niche in comedy. "Although claims about 'firsts' always seem disputable when it comes to the history of film, a case can be made that the first film was a comedy – depending on whether one dates Fred Ott's Sneeze as having been made in 1889 or 1892" (Carroll, 1991, p. 25). Whether actually the first movie ever made or not, comedies were very common theme of early cinema. They were shot in High Key, with ample exterior light, and were often physical in nature, gravitating towards roughhouse and slapstick. High Key lighting allows the viewer to clearly see all of the visual space and is lit flat with no shadows, leaving a sense of safety and positivity.

Sound became commercially popular in 1927, when panchromatic film stock equally sensitive to the entire all light spectrum allowed filmmakers to use tungsten light on set as opposed to the noisy and dangerous carbon arc lights. This enabled filmmakers to be able to record sound on set and comedic plots began to have dialogue. In the 1930's the screwball comedy became very popular, building comedic tension through a "Battle of the Sexes" type plot line. This style of comedy has evolved into the Romantic Comedy, but the lighting style, High Key, has not changed. "They are bright, generally set in affluent or fairly affluent environments, where no one lurks in the shadow and everything is bright and visible, even during night scenes" (Frost, 2009, p. 135).

Low Key

Low Key lighting, though previously used in the theater, transferred onto film with the genre of Film Noir. With its high contrast, dark shadows, and half lit sets and faces, it is said to have "originated in America, emerging out of the synthesis of hard boiled fiction and German expressionism" (Naremore, 2008, p. 9) in the 1920's. Low Key features stylistic sculpting of dark shadow and bright light. It became popular between 1941 and 1958 - but it is still used today (Silver & Ward, 1992). This is coincidentally the same year panchromatic film stock allowed filmmakers more freedom with interior lighting set ups. Coined Film Noir, or Dark Film in 1946 by French critics, this movement became popularized by cineastes of the French new wave movement. The genre is associated with Low-Key lighting, wet down city streets, and *Femme Fatales*

(French for deadly women). "Stylistically shadows prevail, characters walk out of darkness with slashes of shadow across their faces, even during the day, darkness is the predominant feeling. Pessimism and doom are certainties" (Frost, 2009, p. 140). Based on the literature, the following is predicted:

Available Light

Light existing naturally within a given area. Documentaries, independent films, and low-budget productions are often shot using only available light (K & ferncase, 1995, p. 8). One of the latest narrative genres of film to emerge around 2002, developed out of the advancing technology and the commercial accessibility of the digital video camera. Labeled Mumblecore of the 1990's, the name "is the flippant term for any number of recent micro-budget American independent films that favor low-key realism over technical fireworks" (Woodward, 2011, p. D7). Almost a combination of documentary, traditional narrative, and reality television, these movies use only available lighting, allegedly giving them a very real life, gritty quality and tone, even though they are fictional stories. With the proliferation of amateur styles of filmmaking, via the Internet and reality television, these movies have had success in the Independent filmmaking world. "Quickly gaining ground in the film-festival circuits and Netflix queues across the country, these films combine art house aspirations with reality television directness" (Maerez, 2007, p. 82). Available Light tends to make the story believable to audiences and is easy for a filmmaker to use.

Available lighting also is heavily used in reality television shows or any cinema verity that is attempting to transport the viewer into a story that is real or truthful. Available lighting tends to make the viewer believe that he or she is watching a true story. With the development of advancing technology, and increasingly light sensitive phone cameras, it is convincingly easier to bring a sense of reality though lighting and camera operation. Based on this literature, the following hypothesis is posited:

The difference between lighting styles

High-key lighting is a style of lighting for film, television, or photography that aims to reduce the lighting ratio present in the scene. This was originally done partly for technological reasons, since early film and television did not deal well with high contrast ratios, but now is used to suggest an upbeat mood. It is often used in works of comedy. High-key lighting is usually quite homogeneous and free from dark shadows. The terminology comes from the higher balance in the ratio between the key light and the fill light in a traditional three-point lighting setup.

In the 1950s and 1960s, high-key lighting was achieved through multiple light sources lighting a scene usually using three fixtures per person (left, right, and central) which resulted in a uniform lighting pattern with very little modeling. Nowadays, multiple hot light sources are replaced with much more efficient fluorescent or LED soft lights, which provide a similar effect.

The advantage to high-key lighting is that it doesn't require adjustment for each scene which allows the production to complete the shooting in hours instead of days. The primary drawback is that high-key lighting fails to add meaning or drama by lighting certain parts more prominently than others.

Shows with bigger budgets have moved away from high-key lighting by using lighting set-ups different from the three-point standard. Part of the reason for this is the advent of new lighting fixtures that are easier to use and quicker to set up. Another reason is the growing sophistication of the audience for TV programs and the need to differentiate (Pramaggiore).

High-key lighting found its use in classical Hollywood cinema because it was well suited for three-point lighting and other filmmaking traditions. It is an overall lighting design which uses the fill light and backlight to create low contrast between brighter and darker areas. It can be used for both daylight and night scenes (Bordwell, Thompson, Smith, 1979, p. 164).

Genres

Specific lighting styles are intrinsically tied to genres; low-key and high contrast for Film Noir, high-key and low contrast for Comedy, and low-key and available light for Mumblecore or Documentary style films. According to Henri Alekan, a prestigious French cinematographer,

Light becomes mood that gives its tone to a film. It calls upon our memory to react to physical phenomena such as cold, rain, fog, sun, or dryness, and come up with psychological equivalents such as annoyance, sadness, mystery, fear, anguish, comfort, joy, gaiety, etc. As these effects produce immediate impressions in viewers, the cinematographer is able to obtain psychological reactions out of mere technical means (Geuens, 2000, p. 153).

The shadowy low-key lighting effects of Noir provoke viewers to react to plot and characters with a depressive and suspicious frame of mind evoking feelings of danger, suspense, and mystery. The bright high-key lighting in Comedies set viewers in a mood to laugh, see an uplifting plotline, and find characters likeable, whereas the realistic available lighting in Mumblecore films set the viewer up for a story not that unlike their real life with believable characters and plot events.

High Key, Low Key, and Available Light are now used in different types of movies with varying genres, and also in combinations in different kinds of movies. Though they have originated from specific genres and are still generally tied closely to their origin, it is important to note that the label of the genre can be subjective but the actual lighting styles of high key, low key, and available light are specifically defined and are terms used in the field to produce a

cinematographer's desired narrative psychological results. It is predicted that participants will be able to identify genres based on the lighting style.

Lighting and Facial Recognition

Another area that lighting has been examined is facial recognition in real spaces. Hill and Bruce's study on the "Effects of lighting on the perception of facial surfaces" documented a series of experiments that tested participant recognition and likability of faces and objects in different positions and lighting conditions. Though termed differently, the researchers used film lighting techniques in the design. They tested what they called 'top lighting' or overhead lighting in film, a "45 degree light" or key light, and 'bottom lighting' or under lighting on positions of faces, or in film terms, the blocking of faces, in profile, full front, and quarter face positions. Results indicated that participants showed more accuracy and likability when viewing subjects with overhead lighting (Hill & Bruce, 1996). This would support the fact that filmmakers use under lighting to put audiences at unease in mysteries and thrillers, and is a part of the Low Key lighting style.

They also concluded that "When matching faces, changes in lighting directions pose difficulties" (Hill & Bruce, 1996 p. 1001). This finding is supported by Braje et al. (1998) who studied face recognition of full front faces either was "illuminated" or in film terms in High Key lighting, or with 'cast shadows' or Low Key lighting revealed significant data. "Face recognition was found to be sensitive to the presence of cast shadows and to changes in illumination. Observers were slower and less accurate at matching and naming faces when there was a change in illumination direction" (p. 21). Again, these findings support why Filmmakers light High Key for comedies for audience comfort and easy recognition and Low Key for mysteries and movies of suspense to make the audience less able to recognize elements of the movie and keep them on the edge. Together these studies suggest that participants may respond differently to film characters differently when seen in differently lighting conditions.

Research Question 1: Will participants will report feeling differently in the likability of the characters depending on the lighting styles.

Architecture and Film Lighting

Architectural Lighting is the closest field to Film Lighting. These subjects share a similar history, much of the same vocabulary, and the same theory for applied lighting designs on human psychology. Architectural Lighting and Film Lighting both start with the two primal lighting sources, fire and daylight. Early architecture constantly adapted building design to light with natural sunlight and entire rooms were built to align with the sun's rays (Ganslandt & Harald, 1992) just like Tomas Edison's first studio, the Black Maria was built with a retractable roof to film under full sunlight (Brown, 1996). As artificial lighting began, so did the ability to light spaces differently. As technology developed from the oil lamp, to gas lighting, to electrical lighting, many different types of lights, with different color temperatures and strengths, became available.

This allowed for more artistic design, both in architecture and film, which both took their cues from the common source of theater when developing their artistic styles.

Though film and theater lighting have more of a symbiotic relationship as theater was forced to adapt to a more filmic like set with the induction of new lighting technology that was unfavorable to old theater actors, costumes, and painted sets, (Baxter, 1975) the concepts of High Key and Low Key were adopted from theater into as plays were the first to light narratives

according to theme. “Comedies were bright; dramas were uncheerful. Day was yellow; night blue” (Rosenthal & Wertenbaker, 1964, p. 55)

Architecture and Film both use perceptual psychology to get people to see spaces in a certain way. Architecture lighting designers skillfully illuminate buildings and rooms with psychological intentions.

Lighting designers think about psychological response and how behavior is affected by lighting. Some examples are:

1. Visibility of vertical and horizontal junctions aids orientation.
2. People follow the brightest path.
3. Brightness can focus attention.
4. Facing wall luminance is a preference.
5. Lighting can affect body position (Ginthner, accessed April, 2013 p.2).

Psychological Lighting Theory

The High Key, Low Key, and Available Light were created and implemented from the primal development of the human psyche, and even if the film lighting effects have yet to be empirically tested on audiences, psychology has conducted lighting tests in controlled physical environments with significant results. Though psychologists do not use the same terminology as film studies, correlations can be made that suggest if architectural lighting design does have an impact on human interpretation, mood, and behavior in the physical world then it may also have an impact of the audience of a film. Like structural features in within the topic of Media Effects in Communication, aspects of the impact of architectural lighting design on psychological interpretation have been conducted in Psychology.

Different psychological studies proved significant results in varying areas of the human condition. “Light is a pervasive feature of the environment, which exerts broad effects on human behavior” (Sburlea, 2011, p.1). Felix Deutch writes “Every action of light has, in its influence, physical as well as psychic components” (Birren, 1969, p. 400). Slegers et al. (2013) state, after testing two different Dutch elementary school classes in different lighting environments that “the results of our study offer support for the influence of classroom lighting conditions on concentration” (p. 15). Knez (1995) found significant results when measuring mood and memory under different lighting conditions.

The Impact of Lighting Design on Audience Attention

Lighting design in cinema is important due to its influence on the audience and its ability to capture their attention. Light can be used as a tool to direct the viewer's focus onto specific parts of the film. Through changes in lighting, the viewer can be guided towards important details or characters in the story. Lighting can also help determine the meaning and message of the narrative. From dark and shadowy lighting to create tension, to bright lighting that conveys clarity and transformation, this element can assist in interpreting the story. Lighting design plays a significant role in guiding the attention of viewers and enhancing the visual storytelling aspect of the film (Sokari, 2023, p. 4).

Conclusion

Architectural lighting design, facial recognition, advertisements, and the moving image medium of video games have all been psychologically tested for the impact of lighting on human mood, cognition, behavior, or in the very least, preference. Though terminology may differ between the fields of Communication, Film, and Psychology, it should not hinder academic advancement in any field, or other intersecting fields such as Architecture or Marketing. A psychological study of the impact the formal film element of lighting has while communicating narrative plot and character development, not only can, but also should be conducted.

It is finally time for Film Lighting to be empirically tested within Communication. In this study, audience emotional response, and narrative interpretation will be evaluated based upon three basic types of lighting originally seen in the theater of High Key, Low Key, and Available Light. The experiment will isolate the three types of lighting styles from other potential formal element variables, be short in duration, and employ both qualitative and quantitative evaluation methods. The analysis should be conducted utilizing established theories and testing conclusions from different fields that support, explain, or contradict results.

Film lighting is a formal element that is used to create a mood, perception, attention, illusion, and feeling, among many other human cognition manipulations. It is a structural feature that has an impact on the content and creates media effects. It changes psychological perception of people, places, and events, affecting interpretation and emotional response, just as architectural lighting design causes varying human moods and behaviors. It is a phenomenon that is long overdue for testing and analysis, and can help build an academic umbrella over the fields of Communication, Film, Psychology, and Architecture.

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